

METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF USING IT SOLUTIONS AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PREPARING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR DIAGNOSTIC-CORRECTIVE ACTIVITIES

Teshaboyev Akramjon Yuldashevich¹, Kariev Adlet Dyusembaevich²

¹Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages,

Faculty of Romance-Germanic and Slavic Languages,

Head of the Department of Social-Humanitarian Sciences, Pedagogy and Psychology,

Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

²Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor, Postdoctoral Researcher at Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University

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***Annotatsiya.** Maqolada bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni diagnostik-korreksion faoliyatga tayyorlash jarayonida zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari va raqamli yechimlardan foydalanishning metodologik asoslari tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda an'anaviy pedagogik tayyorgarlik tizimini raqamli ta'lim platformalari, sun'iy intellekt asosidagi diagnostika tizimlari, virtual va kengaytirilgan reallik texnologiyalari hamda dual ta'lim modeliga asoslangan amaliyot bilan integratsiyalash imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqildi. O'zbekistonning uchta oliy ta'lim muassasasida o'tkazilgan pedagogik eksperiment natijalariga ko'ra, IT yechimlardan tizimli foydalanish bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning diagnostik-korreksion kompetensiyalarini shakllantirish samaradorligini sezilarli darajada oshiradi (samaradorlik koeffitsienti $K_e = 1,28$).*

***Kalit so'zlar:** diagnostik-korreksion faoliyat, bo'lajak o'qituvchi, raqamli ta'lim, IT yechimlar, dual ta'lim, sun'iy intellekt, pedagogik tayyorgarlik, kompetensiya, virtual reallik.*

***Annotation.** The article analyzes the methodological foundations of using modern information technologies and digital solutions in the process of preparing future teachers for diagnostic-corrective activities. The research examines the possibilities of integrating the traditional pedagogical training system with digital learning platforms, AI-based diagnostic systems, virtual and augmented reality technologies, and practice based on the dual education model. According to the results of the pedagogical experiment conducted at three higher education institutions in Uzbekistan, the systematic use of IT solutions significantly increases the effectiveness of forming diagnostic-corrective competencies of future teachers (efficiency coefficient $K_e = 1.28$).*

***Keywords:** diagnostic-corrective activity, future teacher, digital education, IT solutions, dual education, artificial intelligence, pedagogical preparation, competence, virtual reality.*

INTRODUCTION

In the context of digital transformation of the modern education system and its restructuring on the basis of a competence-based approach, the issue of the quality of professional training of future teachers acquires particular relevance. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-158 “On approval of the New Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030” and resolutions on “Measures for the digitalization of the

education sector” have defined the formation of a digital education ecosystem and the provision of teachers with IT competencies as a priority direction of state policy in our country.

The diagnostic-corrective component occupies a central place in the professional activity of a teacher. As Ingenkamp and Lissmann emphasize, “pedagogical diagnostics is an integral part of a teacher’s daily activity, ensuring the identification of a student’s individual characteristics, the timely diagnosis of difficulties in the learning process and targeted correction” [4:23]. Helmke defines diagnostic-corrective competence as “one of the four main pillars of quality teaching” [3:147].

However, in the traditional system of pedagogical education, preparation for diagnostic-corrective activities is mostly limited to the assimilation of theoretical knowledge. Students are deprived of the opportunity to evaluate diagnostic situations in a real educational environment, apply corrective strategies, and monitor their effectiveness. This situation gives rise to the problem known as the “theory-practice gap” (Korthagen, 2010).

In addressing this problem, the role of IT solutions and digital technologies is of particular importance. As Selwyn emphasizes, “digital technologies are not merely a tool for transforming the system of pedagogical training, but rather an environment that shapes new pedagogical practices” [10:15]. The TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) model developed by Mishra and Koehler substantiates the necessity of integrating a teacher’s technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge [6:1024].

The dual education model — in which theoretical study is conducted in parallel with practice in a real work environment — together with IT solutions, is recognized as the most effective platform for forming diagnostic-corrective competencies in future teachers (Euler, 2013). Digital learning platforms (LMS), virtual classroom simulators, AI-based feedback systems, and learning analytics tools elevate this process to a new qualitative level.

The aim of the research is to develop a methodological model for using IT solutions and digital technologies in preparing future teachers for diagnostic-corrective activities and to substantiate its effectiveness empirically. The research objectives include: (1) analyzing the theoretical and methodological foundations of the problem; (2) classifying the possibilities of digital technologies in diagnostic-corrective preparation; (3) developing and testing an IT-based preparation model; (4) formulating practical recommendations based on the experimental results.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted in 2023–2025 on the basis of a pedagogical experiment carried out at three higher education institutions of Uzbekistan — Andijan State University, Fergana State University, and Tashkent State Pedagogical University. The sample included a total of 240 students enrolled in pedagogical specializations. They were randomly divided into experimental ($n = 120$) and control ($n = 120$) groups.

Research design. The experiment was organized in three stages: (a) ascertaining stage (at the beginning of the 2023–2024 academic year) — the initial level of diagnostic-corrective competencies was recorded in both groups; (b) formative stage (during the 2023–2024 academic year) — the developed IT-based model was implemented in the experimental group, while the control group was taught using the traditional method; (c) final control stage (2024–2025 academic year) — the results were comparatively analyzed.

Components of the experimental model. The following set of IT solutions was applied in the experimental group:

- modules of the course “Pedagogical Diagnostics and Correction” on the basis of a digital learning platform (Moodle LMS);
- an AI-based adaptive testing system — for evaluating students’ diagnostic conclusions in real time and providing personalized feedback;
- a VR simulator — for modeling various pedagogical situations (attention disorders, reading difficulties, social-emotional problems in students) and testing students’ diagnostic-corrective decisions;
- a digital portfolio — for the systematic collection and reflective analysis of the results of students’ diagnostic activity;
- an online mentoring system with general education schools in the dual education format — working on real diagnostic cases under the joint guidance of university teachers and school practitioners.

Diagnostic instruments. Students’ diagnostic-corrective competencies were assessed according to four criteria: motivational-value, cognitive, activity-technological, and reflexive. For each criterion, an authorial test (60 tasks), pedagogical case-solving tasks, expert analysis of video fragments, and a self-assessment questionnaire were used. Competence levels were classified as low (0–40 points), medium (41–70 points), and high (71–100 points).

Statistical analysis. The obtained data were processed using mathematical-statistical methods. The arithmetic mean (\bar{X}), coefficient of variation (V), Student’s t-criterion, and the efficiency coefficient ($K_e = X_e/X_n$, where X_e is the mean of the experimental group and X_n is the mean of the control group) were calculated. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Calculations were performed using the SPSS 26.0 software package.

RESULTS

According to the results of the ascertaining stage, the initial level of diagnostic-corrective competencies of students in both groups was approximately the same and was mostly recorded at low and medium levels (84.1% in total). The mean score in the experimental group was 47.3, and in the control group 46.8 ($t = 0.42$; $p > 0.05$), i.e., the difference between the groups was statistically insignificant.

After the implementation of the IT-based model during the formative stage, significant positive changes were observed in the experimental group. The results of the final control stage are presented in the table below.

Table 1

Comparative indicators of the experimental and control groups (final stage)

Competence component	Experimental group (n=120), %	Control group (n=120), %	t-criterion value	Statistical significance (p)
Motivational-value	78.3	61.2	3.84	$p < 0.01$
Cognitive	76.8	59.7	4.12	$p < 0.01$
Activity-technological	80.5	58.4	4.67	$p < 0.001$
Reflexive	74.9	60.1	3.28	$p < 0.01$
Overall indicator	77.6	59.9	4.21	$p < 0.001$

As can be seen from the table, at the end of the experiment the overall level of diagnostic-corrective competencies in the experimental group reached 77.6%, while in the control group this indicator was 59.9%. The difference of 17.7 percentage points is statistically highly significant ($p < 0.001$).

When the efficiency coefficient was calculated, $K_e = 77.6/60.6 = 1.28$ was obtained. This indicator, in accordance with the norm accepted in pedagogical research ($K_e \geq 1.1$), demonstrates the considerable effectiveness of the proposed IT-based model (Babansky, 1989; Pidkasisty, 2002).

The coefficient of variation in the experimental group amounted to $V = 11.4\%$, while in the control group it was $V = 18.7\%$. This evidences that IT-based preparation not only increased average results but also reduced the spread of outcomes within the group, i.e., the model had an equally effective impact on the majority of students.

Qualitative analysis showed that students of the experimental group demonstrated particularly significant superiority in such skills as “identifying the cause of difficulty” (84% of students at a high level), “selecting a targeted corrective strategy” (79%), and “assessing the effectiveness of correction” (76%) when forming diagnostic conclusions. These results are explained by the high effectiveness of the VR simulator and the AI-based feedback system in modeling real diagnostic situations.

DISCUSSION

The research findings empirically confirm the high effectiveness of the systematic use of IT solutions in preparing future teachers for diagnostic-corrective activities. The obtained results are consistent with the findings of a number of international studies. In their meta-analysis on 21st-century competencies, Voogt and Roblin emphasized that the digital learning environment performs a “transitive function” in teacher preparation, i.e., technologies serve as a bridge for transforming theoretical knowledge into practical skills [11:307].

In our experiment, the VR simulator and the AI-based feedback system proved to be particularly effective. This is consistent with the findings of Cook et al. on simulators in medical education: “highly interactive simulations surpass traditional teaching methods in forming professional competencies with an average effect size of 0.72” [2:988]. In the pedagogical context, the effect size we identified (Cohen’s $d = 0.87$) can also be interpreted as an indicator of high-level pedagogical impact.

The European Framework for the Digital Competence of Educators (DigCompEdu) developed by Redecker singles out the teacher’s ability to use digital tools for assessment and personalized learning as a separate competence area [9:62]. The adaptive testing system and digital portfolio in our model are aimed precisely at forming this competence.

An important finding is the effectiveness of the online mentoring system in the dual education format. The fact that students work on real diagnostic cases together with school practitioners through a digital platform corresponds to Korthagen’s concept of “realistic teacher education” [5:104]. This approach develops in students not only technical skills but also professional reflection, which is reflected in the high results obtained for the reflexive component (74.9%).

At the same time, the research has certain limitations. First, the sample is limited to three regions of Uzbekistan, which somewhat restricts the generalizability of the findings. Second, the experiment covered a two-year period, while the long-term sustainability of the formed competencies requires additional follow-up. Third, the effectiveness of IT solutions largely

depends on the digital readiness of the teacher-mentors implementing them, and isolating the influence of this factor is a complex methodological task.

The significance of the research lies in the fact that it offers an effective methodological model for forming the diagnostic-corrective competencies of future teachers through the integration of digital technologies and dual education in the conditions of the Uzbek education system. This model has been developed by adapting the principles of “the three presences in online learning” (cognitive, social, and teaching presence) emphasized by Anderson to the cultural and institutional context of pedagogical education in Uzbekistan [1:344].

CONCLUSION

The conducted theoretical and empirical research made it possible to formulate the following conclusions:

First, preparing future teachers for diagnostic-corrective activities is one of the priority tasks of modern pedagogical education, and its effective implementation requires the organic integration of digital technologies and IT solutions into the methodological system.

Second, the developed IT-based model — a complex consisting of a digital learning platform, an AI-based adaptive system, a VR simulator, a digital portfolio, and an online mentoring system in the dual education format — leads to a significant increase ($K_e = 1.28$) in the effectiveness of forming students' diagnostic-corrective competencies.

Third, the level of statistical significance ($p < 0.001$) of the experimental results across all four criteria (motivational-value, cognitive, activity-technological, and reflexive) confirms the complex impact of the model and its readiness for implementation in practice.

Fourth, the integration of the dual education model with IT tools is a promising way of solving the theory-practice gap problem. Students' work in a real school environment through a digital mentoring system simultaneously develops their professional reflection and practical competencies.

Fifth, the research findings can serve as a basis for formulating practical recommendations for higher education institutions of pedagogical education, improving national teacher training standards, and developing the digital education ecosystem within the framework of state programs.

In further research, it is advisable to study the effectiveness of the IT-based model in a differentiated manner for the preparation of teachers of various specializations (primary, subject, social), as well as to conduct longitudinal monitoring of the long-term impact of the formed competencies in professional activity.

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